

SOME REACTIONS OF CARBOXYLIC ACIDS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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The phenomenon of so-called "activation" of oxalic acid by the addition of $KMnO_4$ in deficiency in aqueous solution is not shown by other polycarboxylic acids. Enhanced reducing power towards certain metallic salts, such as mercuric chloride and gold chloride (chloroauric acid) thereby acquired, has hitherto been erroneously regarded as being the result of a process of chemical induction. The experimental results can be explained, however, by the formation of intermediate oxidation products of varying degrees of stability; in general, oxy-carboxylic acids which strongly reduce certain metallic salts. The reactions are stoichiometric in nature and thus have nothing in common with the permanganate-oxalate-mercuric chloride reaction.

The reaction between oxalic acid and gold chloride is exceptional, in as much as it is strongly retarded both in light and in the dark by oxygen.

So-called photochemical after-effects, in those cases in which they have actually been confirmed, are also due to the presence of definite stable products formed in the photochemical reaction with halogens.

The present investigation was prompted by the results observed in the permanganate-oxalate-mercuric chloride reaction; it was thought desirable to examine more closely how other simple polycarboxylic acids reacted to similar treatment with permanganate and whether they became "activated" thereby i.e. their power of reducing certain metallic salts was enhanced. Moreover, some of these acids, in particular citric, malic and tartaric, have been stated to exhibit the phenomenon of photochemical after-effect when halogenated in light, in a manner similar to the reaction between iodine and oxalate, but no general mechanism has been suggested to account for the observed results.

These reactions have been studied by Dharr (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 699) who found that the addition of $KMnO_4$ promoted reaction with $HgCl_2$ and thus regarded them as examples of chemical induction, where $KMnO_4$ was supposed to act as an inductor. The experiments were carried out at 100° and the extent of reaction measured by the weight of calomel precipitated. At this temperature, however, it is well known that tartaric, malic, malonic and citric acids are all oxidised, among other products, to formic acid, which reduces $HgCl_2$ quantitatively. They cannot therefore be regarded as induced reactions.

We find that at room temperature (about 20° to 25°) a very slow reduction takes place in the dark (it must not be overlooked that mixtures of these acids and $HgCl_2$ are photosensitive to diffused light) on addition of $KMnO_4$ to the aqueous solutions. All the acid mixtures examined produced calomel, except citric acid, in the case of which the precipitate does not contain calomel in appreciable amounts but consists of a complex insoluble substance which yields on washing with hot water both Cl and a carboxylate. At 100° the precipitate is exclusively calomel.

We have been able to show experimentally that at room temperature acetone dicarboxylic acid, formed as an intermediate product by the action of $KMnO_4$ on citric acid, reacts slowly in solution with $HgCl_2$, forming a similar complex substance. A similar reaction between citric acid and $HgSO_4$ has already been described by Deniges (*Compt. rend.*, 1899, 128, 680) producing the complex $Hg_2O_2SO_4 \cdot 2[(CH_2)_2CO(CO_2)]Hg$. It is clear that the reactions of these carboxylic acids treated with $KMnO_4$ are of a different character to the phenomena associated with the so-called activation of oxalic acid, and that the activity observed with the former is due to the presence of reactive oxidation products.

In view of the unsuitability of HgCl_2 , as a reagent, owing to the possibility of formation of complexes, a further series of experiments was carried out, using gold chloride in its place.

Reduction of gold chloride by organic acids with and without the addition of KMnO_4 , has also been studied by Dhar (*loc. cit.*), who found a considerable enhancement of the rate of reaction to take place. These were also considered to be induced reactions by the author.

It was soon evident, however, that these cannot be induced reactions, since we found that the same reducing power was retained in solutions after all the permanganate had been used up *i.e.* reduced to the Mn^{II} state. This again suggested the presence of intermediate oxidation products formed by the action of permanganate on the acids under investigation, and such has actually proved to be the case. It must also be emphasised that the reactions between the pure acids and gold chloride are highly sensitive to the diffused light of the laboratory, so that comparable results can only be obtained in the dark.

EXPERIMENTAL

The analytically pure acids employed were recrystallised from conductivity water.

5 C.c. of the $N/10$ acids (except in the case of malonic acid where the concentration was 0.4 N) were treated with 0.5 c.c. of $N/10\text{-KMnO}_4$ and 2 c.c. gold chloride (as HAuCl_4) containing 1.8 g. Au per litre, were added at known intervals to the mixture, the whole being made up to 25 c.c. The experiments were carried out at room temperature (about 20°) except in the case of malonic acid, where the reaction was very slow, and the temperature in consequence had to be raised to 30° .

In some of the experiments carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen, the same apparatus was employed as that mentioned in a previous communication (MacMahon and Lal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 143), the time required for the reduction of gold chloride being noted after mixing the reagents in the sealed reaction vessel. Oxalic, citric, malic, tartaric and malonic acids were investigated in this manner.

Effect of Light.—Other things being equal, Table I shows the order of sensitivity in light and comparative rate of reaction in the dark of equivalent concentrations of the above mentioned acids in reducing gold chloride. The figures show the time taken in *minutes* for an arbitrarily selected depth of colour of reduced gold to appear.

TABLE I

	Oxalic.	Citric.	Malic.	Tartaric.	Malonic.
Sunlight	2	3½	4½	10	35
Diffused light	8	30	50	120	40
Dark	20	160	5 hrs.	2 days	39

(approx.) (approx.)

TABLE II

	Oxalic.	Citric.	Malic.	Tartaric.	Malonic.
Air	8	29	50	110	43
Nitrogen	½	60	105	210-220	85

Table I reveals that there is practically no photochemical acceleration in the case of malonic acid. Pre-illumination of the reactants separately does not produce any effect on the time of reduction.

Effect of Atmospheric Oxygen.—Table II shows that in diffused light the reaction is largely retarded by oxygen in the case of oxalic acid, while in the case of the other acids it is somewhat accelerated. If these reactions are carried out in the dark under nitrogen, they are not affected by oxygen, except oxalic acid, where retardation is also observed.

Thus 5 c.c. of *N*/10-oxalic acid and 2 c.c. of gold chloride made up to 25 c.c. gave the following results in the dark.

TABLE III

Temp.	Time for reduction	
	in air	under nitrogen.
3°	70 min.	15
20°	20	$\frac{1}{2}$
35°	$2\frac{1}{2}$	Immediate

Effect of Temperature and Concentration of Acid.—Increase of temperature and concentration, as is to be expected, increases the rate of reduction, but the relative values remain unchanged as given in Table I and figures are therefore not given.

Effect of Addition of KCl or NaCl.—The effect of addition of these salts is to stabilise gold chloride by the formation of a co-ordination complex (Lenher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 546) and the rate of reduction is thus proportionately decreased. With large excess of the salts the photoreaction in diffused light is suppressed.

Hydrogen Peroxide.—It has been stated by Sonstadt (*Chem. News*, 1898, 77, 74) that hydrogen peroxide is produced in small amounts when gold chloride is reduced in aqueous solution. By reducing the latter with carboxylic acids and removing the colloidal gold by shaking with freshly precipitated aluminium hydroxide in the cold and filtering, we have not been able to confirm the presence of H_2O_2 in the filtrates. Traces of H_2O_2 in aqueous solution are not removed by aluminium hydroxide.

Effect of $KMnO_4$.—The reaction between gold chloride and the carboxylic acids is accelerated by the addition of small quantities of $KMnO_4$, but when the gold chloride is added to the mixture, immediately after the latter has been completely reduced, the rate of reaction is found to be at its maximum.

TABLE IV

	Oxalic.	Citric.	Malic.	Tartaric.	Malonic.
Without $KMnO_4$	3 min.	30 min.	50 min.	120 min.	40 min.
$KMnO_4$ added together with $ANCl_3$	9*	8	40	80	32
$ANCl_3$ added after the decolourisation of $KMnO_4$	5	$\frac{1}{2}$	8	30	20

*Oxalic acid is an exception.

By increasing the quantity of $KMnO_4$, the rate of reaction is still further increased.

TABLE V

	Oxalic.	Citric.	Malic.	Tartaric.	Malonic.
0.5 C.c. of $KMnO_4$ (<i>N</i> /10) decolourised	5 (0.2 c.c. $KMnO_4$)	$\frac{1}{2}$	8	30	20
0.75 C.c. of $KMnO_4$ (<i>N</i> /10) decolourised	4.15 (0.2 c.c. $KMnO_4$)	$\frac{1}{2}$	6 $\frac{1}{2}$	25	16

It is clear from these tables that $KMnO_4$ is not an inductor, but that the reaction must be due to the formation of oxidation products highly reactive towards gold salts. The effect of possible oxidation products such as H_2O_2 , aldehydes, acetone and formic acid, as well as Mn^{II} ions, added in amounts corresponding to the concentration of $KMnO_4$ employed, were all found to be negligible.

Change of Reducing Power of the Decolourised Solutions (KMnO₄ and carboxylic acid) with Time.—Gold chloride was added to the aqueous solutions of the acids, previously oxidised with KMnO₄, at varying intervals of time.

TABLE VI

	Citric.	Malic.	Tartaric.	Malonic.
Immediately	$\frac{1}{2}$	8	30	20
After 1 day	1'20	14	45	30 (after 15 min.)
After 2 days	2'15	16	50	38 (after 30 min.)
After 3 "	3'20	18	54	
After 4 "	4'05	19	60	
After 5 "	5'30	20	—	
After 8 "	6'30	23	80	
After 14 "	20	41	—	

It is well known that all these organic acids, except oxalic, are ultimately oxidised to formic acid by KMnO₄, but the above behaviour suggests that when there is a deficiency of the latter, intermediate oxidation products of varying degrees of stability are formed which reduce gold chloride rapidly.

Citric Acid.—Kuyper (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1722) suggested that citric acid was oxidised by KMnO₄ to formic acid with the intermediate formation of acetone dicarboxylic acid.

We have prepared this acid by the method of Pechmann (*Annalen*, 1899, 281, 156), and found that 5 mg. of the crystals dissolved in 25 c.c. of water reduced gold chloride instantly. Its presence in solutions of citric acid to which KMnO₄ has been added has been shown by adding bromine water, when a precipitate appears which has been identified as pentabromoacetone.

Moreover, by adding quantities of the acid, corresponding to the KMnO₄ reduced in the above experiments, to solutions of citric acid and Mn^{II} ions in corresponding concentration, it has been found possible to reproduce exactly the behaviour of citric acid in Table VI.

In aqueous solution the acid decomposes on long keeping to CO₂ and acetone. The results indicate that acetone dicarboxylic acid persists in solution down to vanishingly small concentrations for 14 days or more at 20°.

Malic Acid.—Deniges (*Compt. rend.*, 1900, 130, 32) suggested that malic acid was oxidised to formic acid by KMnO₄ with intermediate formation of oxalacetic acid [HOOC.CH=C(OH).COOH] but this has been questioned by Hatcher and West (*Trans. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, 21, 269).

We have prepared oxalacetic acid by the method of Fenton and Jones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 77), by the action of H₂O₂ on malic acid in presence of FeSO₄. This acid has also been found to reduce gold chloride immediately, but when added to solutions of malic acid and Mn^{II} in the same proportions as above, the same rate of loss of reducing power was not observed. The activity disappeared much more rapidly than in solutions of malic acid treated with KMnO₄, suggesting that an intermediate oxidation product stabler than oxalacetic acid is present and not yet successfully identified.

Tartaric Acid.—Fenton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 68, 899) states that when tartaric acid solutions are treated with KMnO₄ in the presence of small quantities of iron, dioxymaleic acid [HO₂C(COH) : C(OH).COOH] is formed.

We have prepared this acid by Fenton's method and it has also been found to reduce gold chloride very rapidly. It decomposes slowly in aqueous solutions at room temperature to CO_2 and glycol aldehyde (Fenton, *ibid.*, 1896, 69, 546). When added to a mixture of tartaric acid and Mn^{++} ions in small quantities (0.5 mg.), approximately the same rate of loss of reducing power as that observed with KMnO_4 -treated tartaric acid can be reproduced. The corresponding results for these three acids (Table VII) may be compared with Table VI.

TABLE VII

Acid.	Immediately.	Days						
		1	2	3	4	6	8	14
Acetone dicarboxylic	40 sec.	1'45	2'45	3'30	4'15	6'00	7'00	18'00
Oxalacetic	6	10	13	25	38	44	Slow	
Dioxymaleic	27	45	48	53	61	—	75	

The formation of dioxymaleic acid by KMnO_4 has, however, been disputed by Hatcher and West (*Trans. Roy. Soc.*, 1926, 20, 327) so that the question of the identity of the acid must remain open at present.

Malonic Acid.—The intermediate oxidation product in this case is very unstable and disappears within half an hour, so that its identification has not yet been found possible.

Oxalic Acid.—The behaviour of this acid is unique, as we have shown the reaction with gold chloride to be inhibited by atmospheric oxygen both in light and in the dark.

Addition of KMnO_4 slightly accelerates the reduction of gold chloride when the latter is added to the nearly decolourised mixture in air. This is to be expected on account of the presence at this stage of the highly reactive $\text{Mn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ ion (MacMahon and Lal, *loc. cit.*) Further investigations are proceeding.

Photochemical "after-effects".—So-called after-effects have been stated to follow the photobromination of citric, malic and tartaric acids (Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 277).

We have confirmed them in the cases of citric and tartaric acids only. Pure recrystallised malic acid and bromine react rapidly in sunlight but show no after-effect. The latter has been observed only with the impure commercially prepared acid. The impurity responsible has not yet been identified.

Work at present in progress indicates that the effects are wholly due to the presence of definite stable products formed in the course of the photoreaction; with citric acid, pentabromoacetone; with tartaric acid, an oxidation product, possibly aldehyde-tartronic acid or an isomer of this acid (*vide* Ciusa and Piergallani, *Atti. R. Acad. Lincei*, 1914, 7, 23, 1, 811).

An after-effect has also been observed with sodium citrate and iodine (Dhar, *loc. cit.*).

We find, however, that under the conditions stated by Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1308; 1929, 33, 850) no measurable reaction takes place in visible light when the reactants are carefully purified, but that there is strong photocatalysis in the presence of traces of manganese and less so in the presence of iron. This reaction shows an after-effect. In the course of the photoreaction a solid substance is precipitated which appears to be identical with the hexaiodoacetone prepared by Lederer (*Fortschritte der Theerfarbenfabrikation*, 8, 709).

One of us (T. N. S.) is highly thankful to the Lucknow University for the award of a research fellowship which enabled him to undertake the work.